

CBEES

State of the Region Report

2024

A World Order in Transformation?

A Comparative Study of Consequences of the War
and Reactions to these Changes in the Region

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and Reactions to these Changes in the Region

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Contents

7	Preface. The Effects of the War, <i>Anna Maria Jönsson</i> and <i>Per Bolin</i>	150	Hungary. The Government's Views on Russia's Aggression – and Its Consequences, <i>Tamás Csiki Varga</i>
9	Introduction. A World Come Undone? The War in Ukraine and Geopolitical Orientations in Central and Eastern Europe, <i>Joakim Ekman</i>	156	Kazakhstan. The War in Ukraine as a Catalysator for the Decolonial Turn in Qazaqstan, <i>Galym Zhussipbek</i>
	ESSAYS	170	Kyrgyzstan. Kyrgyz Migrant Narratives Amidst Russia's Invasion of Ukraine, <i>Aksana Ismailbekova</i> and <i>Zinaida Almazbekova</i>
15	“A More Just World Order” in the Regime Ideology of Putinism, <i>Mikhail Suslov</i>	177	Latvia. Changing Policies Towards the Russo-phone Community and Its Presence in the Public Sphere, <i>Lelde Luika</i>
23	Confronting Epistemic Injustice: Centering Ukraine in the Paradigm Shift in East European Studies, <i>Vitaly Chernetsky</i>	186	Moldova. A Society Under Pressure: Internal Vulnerabilities and Multiple External Risks, <i>Inna Shupac</i>
31	The “Peaceful Atom” No More: Russia's Invasion, Nuclear Risks, and Weakening Security, <i>Tatiana Kasperski</i>	192	Poland. Russia's Full-Scale Invasion of Ukraine – A Gamechanger For Poland's Position In The Region?, <i>Jakub Bornio</i>
37	Securitization of Orthodoxy in the Baltic States, <i>Alar Kilp</i>	198	Romania. Challenges in the Ukrainian-Romanian Relations and Romania's Future Geostrategic Position, <i>Ana Maria Albulescu</i>
44	Cooperation in the Baltic Sea region at the Critical Juncture, <i>Kazimierz Musiał</i> and <i>Damian Szacawa</i>	205	Russia. Russian Higher Educational Institutions “Effective Managers of War”, <i>Dmitry Dubrovskiy</i>
51	The EU's Eastern Policy Under Change, <i>Tomasz Stępniewsk</i>	214	Slovakia. The Slovak 2023 Parliamentary Elections: A Once-in-a-Lifetime Opportunity for a Political Comeback?, <i>Miroslav Pažma</i> and <i>Steven Saxonberg</i>
55	The Post-Invasion Disarray in the Balkans, <i>Edward P. Joseph</i>	228	Sweden. The Swedish Response to the War in Ukraine: The Example of Psychological Defense, <i>Ola Svenonius</i>
64	The CSTO Parliamentary Assembly: Authoritarian Legal Harmonization in Eurasia, <i>Oleg Antonov</i> , <i>Edward Lemon</i> , <i>Bo Petersson</i> , and <i>Olena Podolian</i>	236	Turkey. The Conflict in Ukraine and AKP's Foreign Policy: Implications for Turkish Identity and Nationhood, <i>George Dyson</i> and <i>Yasemin Gülsüm Acar</i>
69	South Caucasus Amidst the Epochal Turn of the Century, <i>Shota Kakabadze</i>	244	Ukraine. The Human Face of Ukrainian Resilience, <i>Yuliya Yurchuk</i> and <i>Kateryna Zarembo</i>
	COUNTRY REPORTS	253	Ukraine. Evidence from Ukrainian Municipalities: The Importance of Collaborative Crisis Governance, <i>Oleksandra Keudel</i>
75	Armenia. The Impact of Russia's War in Ukraine on the Nagorno-Karabakh Conflict and Armenia, <i>Sossi Tatikyan</i>	261	Conclusion. The Fog of War, the Fog of Peace, <i>Irina Sandomirskaja</i>
90	Azerbaijan. The End to “Balancing” Foreign Policy? Why the Invasion of Ukraine Matters for Azerbaijan, <i>Sofie Bedford</i> , and <i>Nurlan Aliyev</i>	265	List of Authors
99	Belarus. A Silent Death: The Destruction of Academic Scholarship in Belarus, <i>Aliaksei Lastouski</i> , and <i>Per Anders Rudling</i>		
109	Bosnia-Herzegovina. The War in Ukraine. Its Geopolitical and Emotional Effects for Bosnia and Herzegovina, <i>Belma Becirbasic</i> and <i>Johanna Mannergren</i>		
116	Bulgaria. The Consequences of the War in Ukraine in Bulgaria: Political, Economic, and Cultural Divides, <i>Emilia Zankina</i>		
125	Czech Republic. The Splendor and Misery of the Czech Welcome to Ukrainian Refugees, <i>Marie Jelínková</i>		
132	Finland. An Epochal Turn of the Defense Policy, <i>Markku Kivinen</i>		
142	Germany. A Decisive Watershed for Germany and a Turning Point for Europe, <i>Susan Lindholm</i> and <i>Ann-Judith Rabenschlag</i>		

Preface

The Effects of the War

The Centre for Baltic and East European Studies (CBEES) was founded in 2005 at Södertörn University, Stockholm. The centre promotes and develops research and doctoral studies on the Baltic Sea region and Central and Eastern Europe. CBEES organizes conferences, workshops, webinars, public lectures and a series of Advanced seminars. Its academic staff consists of professors, research coordinators, postdocs, guest researchers and PhD students connected to the graduate school BEEGS. CBEES also publishes *Baltic Worlds*, a quarterly scholarly journal which, like this Report and CBEES itself, is funded by the Swedish Foundation for Baltic and East European Studies (*Östersjöstiftelsen*).

The CBEES State of the Region Report is an annual publication, reporting and reflecting on social and political developments in the Baltic Sea Region and Eastern Europe, each year taking a new topical perspective. The first report, covering events in 2020, focused mainly on constructions and reconstructions of national historical memory in the region and the various forms of instrumentalizing the past. The 2021 report made a wide comparative study of Far-Right movements in the region, and their connection to populist politics and tendencies towards authoritarianism. The 2022/23 report instead focused on the challenges posed by environmental issues: how the different states in the region handles matters connected to pollution, mismanagement of natural resources, the effects of climate change and the problems connected to garbage deposits and nuclear waste.

This year's report concerns the far-ranging and pivotal changes caused by Russia's war against Ukraine. In a wide overview of the entire region, different political, social, and cultural effects of the war are detailed and analyzed. It seems that we are now returning to a polarized world order, with Putin's Russia bent towards neo-imperialism, isolationism, and increasing authoritarianism, tendencies that clearly produced the ongoing war and have fundamentally changed the political landscape in the entire region for the foreseeable future. While this unjust war is naturally hardest for the fighting nation of Ukraine, its effects are much more far-reaching and in need of a thorough and comprehensive analysis. We are confident that this report will be a vital part of that endeavor.

Ninna Mörner has edited the report, with the assistance of CBEES researchers Joakim Ekman, Irina Sandomirskaja, Yulia Gradskova, Julia Malitska, Tora Lane and Cagla Demirel. We hope that the report will stimulate debate within the academic community as well as public discussion on these very crucial matters. ●

”

In a wide overview of the entire region, different political, social, and cultural effects of the war are detailed and analyzed.

Anna Maria Jönsson

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The content expresses the views of the authors and does not necessarily reflect the views of the editor, the editorial group or CBEES, the Centre for Baltic and East European Studies and Södertörn University.

Introduction

A World Come Undone?

The War in Ukraine and Geopolitical Orientations in Central and Eastern Europe

by **Joakim Ekman**

The unprovoked Russian attack on Ukraine, growing US–China rivalry, and the Israel– Hamas war have had profound effects on what is conventionally referred to as the world order. Presently, the prospects for the arrangement of a global order based on the principles of liberal democracy, the rule of law, respect for human rights and sustainable economic growth look unrealistic. Instead, current assessments of future global trends tend to emphasize the global expansion of authoritarianism, increased geopolitical competition and economic protectionism.¹ This does not mean that the world is falling apart, but it certainly means that the capacity for dealing with global challenges (such as climate change and world poverty) has suffered.

Moreover, one might argue that the entire post-communist period finally came to an end with the outbreak of war in February 2022, although some have argued that this happened already in 2014 with the Russian invasion of the Crimean Peninsula.² Putin’s full-scale invasion of Ukraine fundamentally changed the conditions for international cooperation; and the war has impacted regional stability and threatened the entire project of European integration. Geo-economic fragmentation has emerged as a threat to food and energy security. The aim of the *CBEES State of the Region Report 2024* is to map out reactions to and consequences of the war in contemporary Central and Eastern Europe. We cover countries in all parts of the region: in the Baltics, in Central Europe, in the Balkans, and in Eastern Europe and parts of Central Asia. Also, we have included cases from Scandinavia and

the North: Sweden and Finland, as well as Germany and Turkey. Topics covered here include political issues, primarily relating to security, but also to democracy versus authoritarian rule, as well as environmental protection, migration and demographic changes, and the changing prospects for knowledge production.

Public Opinion and Geopolitical Orientations

The war has made ordinary citizens in Central and Eastern Europe more aware of their geopolitical options. Since 1989, virtually all countries in Eastern Europe have experienced political and economic integration with Western Europe. This involves, in simple terms, exposure to market economy (or neo-liberalism) and democracy, including liberal values, pluralism and minority rights. For some countries, exposure has taken place as either EU candidates or full members, or as members of NATO (or both); for others, the exposure has been limited to trade, tourism, labor migration or culture and mass media.

Previous research has demonstrated a distinct gap between populations in Western Europe and post-communist citizens regarding basic values and attitudes,³ which is further bolstered by a generation gap.⁴ While the culture gap between “East” and “West” has received a lot of scholarly attention in terms of public attitudes towards democracy⁵ and European integration,⁶ there is less research about geopolitical orientations

among ordinary citizens in Central and Eastern Europe (cf. below): meaning in this context, attitudes to the EU versus Russia or, alternatively, attitudes relating to a liberal-democratic Western civilization versus an authoritarian, anti-liberal alternative.⁷ Of course, the dissolution of the Soviet Union brought the issue to the fore. After the Cold War, people's cultural and religious identities were predicted to become the most important sources of conflict in the world.⁸ Moreover, globalization has made geopolitical orientations an intrinsic component of national identity.⁹ Still, it was only with the Russian war, starting with the annexation of Crimea in 2014 and the full-scale invasion in early 2022, that geo-cultural belonging re-emerged as one of the most crucial questions for contemporary European societies.

Existing studies on geopolitical orientations (among ordinary citizens) typically covers public attitudes towards foreign and security policy, perceived borders of the state and the cultural closeness of other countries, including historical relations.¹⁰ One example is O'Loughlin, Toal and Kolosov, who have looked at public beliefs that they live in a “Russian

world” (*Russkii mir*), drawing on public opinion polls from southeastern Ukraine and three Russian-supported de facto states (Abkhazia, South Ossetia, and Transnistria). In that study, geopolitical orientations equal respondents' levels of trust in the Russian president and attitudes towards Russians in general.¹¹ In a similar way, Vardomatsky analyses public opinion in Belarus, drawing on the question “Which union would be better for Belarusians: the European Union or a union with Russia?”¹² Analyzing public geopolitical preferences in Georgia, Moldova and Ukraine, Torres-Adan constructs a four-fold classification where the central distinction is the one between supporters of the Eurasian Economic Union (“Easternizers”) and supporters of the European Union (“Westernizers”).¹³ Onuch and Sasse have analyzed anti-regime protests in Belarus, drawing on online surveys. Here, different geopolitical orientations are understood as foreign policy preferences: support for joining the EU, support for joining the Russian Federation, and agreement/disagreement with the statement that the biggest threat to Belarus is Russia.¹⁴ Finally, drawing on a representative opinion poll from late 2019 and early 2020, O'Loughlin and Toal measure geopolitical orientations among Belarusians by focusing on attitudes

towards future foreign policy alternatives: preference for a neutral position between Russia and the West; support for joining the European Union; preference for staying in the Eurasian Economic Union; support for staying close to both the EU and the EAEU; and locating Belarus on a scale from 0 (the West) to 10 (Russia).¹⁵

However, research focusing on public orientations towards Russia's military aggression against Ukraine is thus far rather limited;¹⁶ even if questions about geopolitical orientations in Europe have become an increasingly more urgent and recognized political issue. The *Eurobarometer* started to include questions about the war in Ukraine in the spring of 2022,¹⁷ and other public opinion surveys on geopolitical orientations have

occasionally been conducted in individual countries.¹⁸ In the West, public opinion has confirmed the negative view of Russia manifested in official policies of denunciation and economic sanctions. Among US citizens, only 9 per cent have a favorable opinion of Russia, which is the lowest score measured by Gallup since 1989. Among NATO allied countries, the corre-

sponding figure is 14 per cent.¹⁹ In Europe, opinions towards Russia and the war in Ukraine seem more divided. This was highlighted in a recent report by the European Council on Foreign Relations.²⁰ According to the ECFR report, two-thirds of Europeans in 10 countries consider Russia as an “adversary” or a rival to their own country (polls from January 2023). This was most notable in Denmark (82 per cent), Estonia and Poland (79 per cent) and Great Britain (77 per cent). The lowest “adversary” stance was found in Romania (44 per cent), whereas in Italy, Portugal, France, Spain, and Germany, the figures hovered around 54 to 69 per cent.²¹ When polled in the summer/early fall of 2023, eight out of 10 Europeans had a distinctly negative perception of Russia; and about as many had no confidence in Putin as a political leader.²²

Patterns of Geopolitical Orientations in Europe

Previous polls by the European Council of Foreign Relations (in 2022) have documented a similar joint condemnation of the war and Russia, but a lot more division about perceptions of how the war would end. Citizens in some countries thought that it would be best to end the war as soon as possible (“peace at any cost”); others felt

“Two-thirds of Europeans in 10 countries consider Russia as an ‘adversary’.”

that the war could not end unless a clear defeat of Russia was a reality (a “justice” orientation). In 2022, the peace camp was larger than the justice camp (particularly in Italy, Germany, Romania and France). Poland was the most obvious supporter of the opposite opinion, and wanted to see Russia punished for its aggression, even if that meant a drawn-out war. However, the ECFR 2023 report demonstrated a general tendency to close ranks to support the idea that Russia must be pushed back and Ukraine regain all of its territory. In 2023, this was manifested among most respondents in Estonia, Poland, Denmark, and Great Britain. In Germany and France, the number of citizens belonging to the “peace camp” dropped significantly. Only in Italy and Romania one could find a majority in favor of the “peace at any costs” option.

What Krastev and Leonard²³ could demonstrate was thus that a standard and taken-for-granted attitudinal East-West difference was not really present in Europe. Rather, three different blocks appear to have emerged. Firstly, there is a north-eastern group of countries (Estonia, Poland, Denmark and Great Britain) where most people strongly support Kyiv's objectives in the war. Secondly, there is an ambiguous group of West European countries (France, Germany, Spain and Portugal), with divided opinions on how the war should end. Thirdly, there is Italy and Romania, in Southern and South-Eastern Europe, with a preference for the war to end as soon as possible.

These regional differences point to the importance of country-specific factors. The countries of Central and Eastern Europe all have longer historical relations to Russia, in different varieties. Some have distinctly negative experiences, and perceive Russia as an oppressor, like the Baltic states (based on post-World War II experiences).²⁴ To others, more distant historical ties rather entail Russia as the liberator from Ottoman rule, making for example Bulgarians more pro-Russian than other East Europeans.²⁵ Serbia too shares a historical background of widespread pro-Russian sentiments, which was partly reinforced by the Kosovo conflict and the NATO intervention in 1999. Hungary admittedly has weaker historical and cultural ties with Russia; but the strong political and economic relationship between Orbán's government and the Kremlin (also after 2022)

“Explicitly pro-Russian sentiments may nevertheless be found in some countries.”

makes the country stand out as a deviant case in the current Central European context. Also, one could point to some “Eastern elements” present in Hungarian society, in addition to the frequently noted self-image of a Christian bulwark: some Hungarian elites promote the notion of Hungary as part of a loosely defined Eurasian community.²⁶

One could of course assume that the region's historical experience of Soviet communism would have resulted in general anti-Russian sentiments and (conversely) pro-Ukrainian sentiments throughout Central and Eastern Europe. While this is true and reflected in for example widespread willingness to help Ukrainian refugees, explicitly pro-Russian sentiments may nevertheless be found in some countries, most notably in Slovakia, Hungary and Bulgaria. A September 2022 poll revealed that more than half of Slovaks would welcome a military victory of Russia over Ukraine.²⁷ In a survey from the spring of 2022²⁸ only 33 per cent of Bulgarians and 45 per cent of Hungarians perceived Russia as a threat. In yet another survey, from the fall of 2022, Hungary, Slovakia, and Bulgaria displayed the weakest support in the region for EU sanctions against Russia.²⁹

Still, looking at opinion polls from the summer/early fall of 2023, we find continued overall support to Ukraine: 86 per cent of EU citizens approve of the EU continuing to provide humanitarian support; 77 per cent welcoming Ukrainian war refugees; and 71 per cent approve of economic sanctions against Russia.³⁰ At the same time, some 77 per cent of Hungarians oppose financing through EU funds. As for Ukraine as a candidate for EU

membership, two thirds (67 per cent) of Europeans are ready to support this (the lowest support levels are found in France and Germany).

Moreover, some 57 per cent of EU citizens think that the EU should support Ukraine with military equipment and training. However, in some countries, this kind of support is low: in Slovakia, 52 per cent of the

respondents oppose military assistance, and a majority of Germans reject the delivery of German cruise missiles to Ukraine.³¹

The Present Report

The *CBEES State of the Region Report* is an annual publication, reporting and reflecting on social and political

developments in the Baltic Sea Region and Eastern Europe, each year taking a new and topical perspective. The report is written by researchers and area specialists, from within the countries of the region covered. The overall purpose of this initiative is to offer a publication that will be of interest to fellow researchers, policy makers, stakeholders, and the general public. The first report, covering events in 2020, focused mainly on constructions or reconstructions of national historical memory in the region and the instrumentalization of the past.³² The second report covered far-right and populist political parties, movements and actors (2021),³³ while the third report focused on environmental issues (in 2022–23).³⁴ how the different states in Central and Eastern Europe handled matters related to pollution, mismanagement of natural resources, the effects of climate change and the problems connected to garbage deposits and nuclear waste. The report also included the Soviet period of mismanagement of natural resources and the general indifference to industrial waste.

The present report deals with consequences of the war. The Russian full-scale military attack on Ukraine, unjustified and unprovoked as it was, has been disastrous and has so far resulted in enormous losses of human life, the displacement of millions, the destruction of cities, civilian and private infrastructure and productive facilities, the demolition of cultural heritage sites, as well as contamination of land and forests. All sectors of Ukraine's economy have suffered losses.³⁵ To the rest of the region, the war has highly impacted energy markets and increased food prices. To some countries, like Poland, Germany and the Czech Republic, refugees from Ukraine have been a new reality.³⁶ To other countries, like Georgia, Armenia, Turkey and Kazakhstan, Russian exiles pose a new challenge.³⁷ But above all, the war has made security a major concern throughout the region, and has increased or reinforced tensions between some countries. This report presents all these challenges, both in the form of thematic pieces and specific country reports.

The thematic section includes Mikhail Suslov's essay on the ideology of Putinism, Vitaly Chernetsky's essay on "epistemic injustice" Tatiana Kasperski's essay on environmental safety risks at Ukrainian nuclear facilities, and an essay on the securitization of Orthodoxy in the three

Baltic States. We also have a few regional overviews, on the Baltic Sea Region (by Damien Scacawa and Kazimierz Musial), on the Balkans (by Edward Joseph), on the EU (by Tomasz Stepniewski), on Central Asia (by Oleg Antonov, Edward Lemon, Bo Petersson and Olena Podolian), and on South Caucasus (by Shota Kakabadze).

The country-by-country section includes chapters on Armenia (by Sossi Tatikyan), Azerbaijan (by Sofie Bedford and Nurlan Ailyev), Belarus (by Per Anders Rudling and Aliaksei Lastouski), Bosnia and Herzegovina (by Belma Becirbasic and Johanna Mannergren), Bulgaria (by Emilia Zankina), Czech Republic (by Marie Jelinkova), Finland (by Markku Kivinen), Germany (by Susan Lindholm and Ann-Judith Rabenschlag), Hungary (by Tamás Csiki Varga), Kazakhstan (by Galym Zhussipbek), Kyrgyzstan (by Aksana Ismailbekova and Zinaida Almazbekova), Latvia (by Lelde Luika), Moldova (by Inna Shupac), Poland (by Jakub Bornio), Romania (by Ana Maria Albulescu), Russia (by Dmitry Dubrovskiy), Slovakia (by Miroslav Pažma and Steven Saxonberg), Sweden (by Ola Svenonius) and Turkey (by George Dyson and Yasemin G. Acar). Ukraine is covered in two reports: on the human face of social resilience

(by Kateryna Zaremba and Yuliya Yurchuk) and on governance during crisis (by Oleksandra Kuedel). In the summary, Irina Sandomirskaja provides a few concluding reflections on the consequences of the war and what we can possibly say about it. ●

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“The Russian full-scale military attack on Ukraine, unjustified and unprovoked as it was, has been disastrous.”

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Introduction

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NOTE: In this report, both the spelling Turkey and the official name Türkiye are used.

Kazakhstan is spelled Qazaqstan in the country report, referring to the contemporary Latinized version of the Kazakh language. However, we use Kazakhstan elsewhere as this is still the spelling officially used.

Essay

Vladimir Putin addresses the plenary session of the World Russian People’s Council with Patriarch Kirill of Moscow. PHOTO: RIA NOVOSTI

“A More Just World Order” in the Regime Ideology of Putinism

by Mikhail Suslov

T

he concept of “a more just world order” represents a relatively recent development within the regime ideology of today’s Russia, which is dubbed “Putinism” in this essay. By 2024, it has emerged as a central element in the argument that the war in Ukraine should be understood as Russia’s combat for international justice against the hegemony of the “global West”. Given its novelty, “a more just world order” remains a work in progress within the ideological landscape. It is marked by some inconsistency and conceptual shallowness, explained by Putinism’s lack of a clear utopian ideal. Nonetheless, the Russian politi-

cal elite is firmly convinced, with good reason, that this concept is a valuable asset, allowing them to draw upon Russia’s intellectual tradition while also aligning with contemporary global agendas such as decolonization, ecological crises, and economic disparities.

Justice as Russia’s “Basic Value”

The Russian intellectual tradition highlights justice as a defining feature of its culture, with grassroots visions of justice emerging in medieval folklore tales about utopian lands like Belovod’e.¹ Unlike their European counterparts, those dreams of justice persisted into modern

The War in Ukraine as a Catalysator for the Decolonial Turn in Qazaqstan

by Galym Zhussipbek

This article aims to shed light on some serious changes in Qazaqstan¹ that have accelerated since the double shock of early 2022 — first, the massive protests of January 2022, “Bloody January”, and the subsequent gradual dismantling of the Nazarbayev regime; second, the full-scale Russian aggression in February 2022 against Ukraine, the country which shares many similarities with Qazaqstan in its pre-Soviet, Soviet and post-Soviet periods. These transformations can be summarized under the phenomenon referred to in this article as “demands for decolonization and decolonial turn” (the definitions will be explored further below).

Both Ukraine and Qazaqstan share a long border with Russia. Therefore, Ukrainians and Qazaqs have a long history of interaction with the Russian state, ranging from cooperation, dialogue and mutual cultural fertilization to dramatic conflicts, subjugation, and colonization. The synergy between the geographical proximity to Russia and the expansionism inherent in both Russian and Soviet states explains why both Ukrainians and Qazaqs were

at the forefront of Russian and Soviet colonial projects, whether it was settler, cultural, linguistic, or industrial and environmental colonization (this factor in particular links Qazaqs and Ukrainians).

On the other hand, in the post-Soviet period of their independence, Ukraine and Qazaqstan were in the unique position of possessing a large arsenal of nuclear weapons and other types of weapons of mass destruction. These countries were pressured to agree to denuclearization in exchange for political assurances, which were, in reality, mere political declarations, codified by the in fact toothless Budapest Memorandum. Ukraine and Qazaqstan (also Belarus, which is beyond the scope of this article) inherited a huge nuclear arsenal from the Soviet period (1 700 nuclear warheads in Ukraine, 1 400 in Qazaqstan). Western countries, especially the USA, exerted enormous pressure on these states to destroy or abandon these weapons and to denuclearize. In 1994, Ukraine and Qazaqstan became denuclearized states in exchange for the assurances of sovereignty and territorial integrity, codified

Demonstrators on the central square of Aktobe, January 4, 2022 (Bloody January).

PHOTO: WIKIMEDIA COMMONS

in the Budapest Memorandum. This document confirmed security assurances in connection with Ukraine’s and Qazaqstan’s accession to the Treaty on the Non-Proliferation of Nuclear Weapons (NPT), signed by Ukraine, Qazaqstan, and the three NPT depositary states, the US, the UK, and the Russian Federation. The signatories agreed to respect Ukrainian (and Belarus’ and Qazaqstan’s) sovereignty and independence within existing borders and to refrain from using force against it.²

In general, the centuries-long history of relations between Qazaqs and the Russian Empire, and then the Soviet state, can be described, at best, as “inherently complicated”.³ Sultan Akimbekov, a prominent Qazaq (of the Russian-speaking cohort), historian, and director of the Institute of Asian Studies in Almaty, has made an incisive analysis: “The Qazaqs have never recognized Russian rule”.⁴ It is noteworthy that the last Qazaq ruler, Kenesary Qassymuly, who was elected Khan at an all-Qazaq “kurultai” in 1841, fought against Russian colonization for ten years until his death.⁵ Mambet Koigeldiev, another prominent Qazaq historian (of the Qazaq-speaking cohort) notes that the Bolsheviks refused to recognize the Qazaqs’ right to self-determination and pursued Russia-centric imperial interests.⁶

Qazaq historians, notably Mambet Koigeldiev, Talas Omarbekov, Beibit Koyshibayev, and Sultankhan Aqqululy,⁷ cite several factors to explain why both Ukrainians and Qazaqs were subjected to different persecutions by the Tsarist and Soviet states for generations. These factors may explain why the war in Ukraine resonates strongly in Qazaq society, which is becoming increasingly familiar with its own history. They include the dynamic and distinct culture and language (both Ukrainians and Qazaqs were denied the proper names of their ethnic-national groups; their native languages were either almost completely wiped out or de facto banned in most areas in large cities and official public spaces), their large populations (Ukrainians were the second largest ethnic group after Russians, while Qazaqs were the most populous Asian and Muslim group in the Russian Empire and the early Soviet state in the period before the Stalinist famine), and the long history of anti-colonial liberation struggle and a strong cohort of anti-colonial thinkers, scholars and local leaders in both Ukraine and Qazaqstan.⁸

In this paper it is suggested that the Soviet state was colonial (see below); therefore it accepts the continuity between Tsarist and Soviet colonization. This position used to be accepted

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In general, the centuries-long history of relations between Qazaqs and the Russian Empire, and then the Soviet state, can be described, at best, as ‘inherently complicated’.

Monument to the Victims of the Famine (*Asharshylyq*, 1931–1933) in Astana. After February 24, 2022, terms of genocide and ethnocide are more often applied in the context of the famine. PHOTO: E-HISTORY.KZ

mainly by small circles of Qazaq-speaking historians and the decolonial intelligentsia, but in recent years it has become increasingly strong and popular among the general population of Qazaqstan, especially among the younger generation. As a result, Qazaq society has increasingly recognized the need for decolonization and decoloniality. And these demands have led to a mental separation of Qazaqstan from the militaristic, expansionist and colonial policies, agenda and psyche of the current Russian regime and its supporters.

The central claims of this article are that solidarity with Ukraine⁹ and the search for decoloniality have a stronghold in Qazaqstan. It is not only the independent, liberal and oppositional thinkers, but also the conservative and pro-status quo Qazaq experts that support Ukraine and openly defend the view that Qazaqstan should be integrated into the democratic world;¹⁰ therefore, we can speak of a mental separation from revisionist Russia and the colonial Soviet past. On the other hand, a kind of sobering up of attitudes to the Western democratic world (which entails disillusionment with its double standards) in the post-2022 period can be observed in Qazaqstan, which can also be analyzed in the context of the decolonial turn.

Decolonial Turn in Qazaqstan

The aggression against Ukraine resonates strongly in Qazaqstan,¹¹ as the direct proximity

to Russia in the areas where the Russian state expanded for centuries has given Ukrainian and Qazaq society similar traumatic historical experiences and common sensitivities. Both are united in their struggle for the preservation of their identity (even in the struggle for a proper name since the Tsarist government deliberately misnamed Ukrainians and Qazaqs for centuries, whereas Soviet Russian society used pejorative names to depict both groups), language, territorial integrity, and sovereignty, including the post-Soviet period. Significantly, according to a survey conducted by Ukrainian experts in 2023, ordinary citizens of Ukraine who do not know the history of the Qazaqs and the political situation in Qazaqstan well have, merely by observing social media and the news, come to believe that the most support for Ukraine in the Central Asian region comes from Qazaqstan and the Qazaqs.¹²

The war launched by Russia against Ukraine catalyzed scholarly and especially public awareness and demands for decolonization and decoloniality in Qazaqstan. Decolonization and decoloniality are not identical concepts. This paper conceptualizes decolonization as a struggle against political and economic colonization. In contrast, decoloniality or decolonial turn is more about the mental, ideational, and cultural struggle against coloniality, which is non-material, at the level of ideas, knowledge, and perceptions.¹³ Taken together, decolonization and decoloniality mean gaining the right as individuals and communities to self-determination and developing their own culture, language, habitat, and society to the level to accept universal human dignity and uphold justice.¹⁴ The Qazaq decolonial turn catalyzed by the war in Ukraine did not emerge in a vacuum. Various anti-colonial and decolonial discourses never disappeared in the Qazaq-speaking segments of Qazaqstan's society, e.g. the “quldyq sana” discourse (in Qazaq, “slave mentality”, in a certain sense “Russified”). Since the late 1980s at the latest, they gradually became part of public and academic discussions. However, the decolonial discourse was initially limited in scope and did

not resonate with the majority, especially the Russian-speaking and urbanized Qazaqs.

According to decolonial scholars, e.g., Walter Mignolo and Rolando Vazquez,¹⁵ one of the main goals of the decolonial turn is to heal colonial wounds. In Qazaqstan, these include: The catastrophic famine of the Stalinist period (called “Asharshylyq” in Qazaq), which, according to estimates made by Qazaq historians, killed nearly half of the ethnic Qazaq population¹⁶; the hierarchies of languages and cultures; the destruction of Qazaq nomadic culture by the Soviets; the eradication of the whole generation of “Alash” intellectuals (progressive native intelligentsia, see below); the marginalization of the Qazaq language in the official public sphere; and defining Qazaq culture and identity as “frozen, monolithic, prone to archaism, patriarchalism and conservatism”. To this can be added the recent dispossession and structural injustice caused by the combination of the authoritarian regime and neoliberal rentier capitalism (the latter is beyond the scope of this paper).

The decolonial turn in Qazaqstan leads to a more comprehensive approach to analyzing and re-conceptualizing Soviet history, nation-building, modernization, industrialization, sedentarization, women's emancipation, the Soviet policy of establishing nuclear test sites and power stations, deportations of entire groups of people, and many other issues through the decolonial lens by taking into account Soviet colonization and post-Soviet colonialities. Qazaqstan's political self-assertion under the changed geopolitical conditions in the world of waning Russian domination, the goal of building a strong political nation, regional identity, and integration in the Central Asia region should also be counted in the Qazaq decolonial turn.

Since its official inception in 2014, the Russia-led Eurasian integration has been described as colonial by independent Qazaq experts and Qazaq businesspersons because of its inherently unfair regulations, e.g., concerning income distribution.¹⁷ Coloniality in relations with the non-democratic revisionist Russian regime was evident for many Qazaq experts and businesspersons long before its aggression against

Ukraine.¹⁸ The highly disadvantageous trade and economic conditions of the Russia-led Eurasian integration for local businesses seriously contribute to raising awareness of the need for political and economic decolonization.

The Qazaq decolonial voice can serve as an important counterargument against the appropriation of the decolonial agenda by Russian ideologues who support the aggression against Ukraine. Also, it can be a timely correction to the obsession of many contemporary decolonial thinkers in the global North and global South with their one-sided critiques of Western capitalism and NATO in the face of the ongoing war in Ukraine and the lack of critical analysis of past (Soviet) and present (revisionist Russian) colonial practices in the wider Eurasian space.

The Colonial Character of the Soviet System: “Red Racism”

After the initial, short-lived, affirmative action policy period, Soviet policy under the rhetorical guise of “friendship of nations” and “internationalism” evolved into a Russian-centric system,¹⁹ which scholars of Ukrainian and Qazaq origin depict as “red racism”.²⁰ There is a growing conviction in Qazaq society that Soviet policy was not only colonial but more harmful and penetrative than the earlier Tsarist colonization. In academia, particularly in the post-February 2022 period, an academic discourse is emerging among a younger generation of scholars of Qazaq origin (Botakoz Kassymbekova, Azamat Junisbai, Madi Kaparov, Togzhan Kassenova, and Aigerim Kussayinkyzy can be named) on Soviet Russo-centrism (depicting it as “red racism”) and post-Soviet Russian revisionism.²¹ However, the view about the colonial nature of the Soviet system and revisionist post-Soviet Russian policies was conceptualized by Qazaq-speaking historians of senior generations (such as Mambet Koigeldiev, Talas Omarbekov, Sultankhan Aqqululy, and others) some time ago. On the other hand, Qazaq historians of different spectrums share a firm conviction that the Soviet power refused to recognize Qazaqs' right to self-determination and replaced this right with class interests that were alien to Qazaq society.²²

“The war launched by Russia against Ukraine catalyzed scholarly and especially public awareness and demands for decolonization and decoloniality in Qazaqstan.”

The Soviet system, despite its self-proclaimed egalitarianism, created a hierarchy of languages and cultures that was Russo-centric. Moreover, this system was premised on the institutions of selective employment, selective and discriminatory housing policies and urbanization ensuing from the hierarchy of ethnic groups.²³ An Afro-American scholar’s analysis of the racialized imagination of Qazaqstan is interesting and insightful, especially her comments about Soviet whiteness and Qazaq foreignness.²⁴ What many decolonial scholars in the “global North” and “global South” have overlooked is that the colonial nature of the Soviet system was evident in its racialized modernization, which reinforced the agrarian characteristic of the Qazaq and other Central Asian societies (inter alia, by “propiska” the segregationist registration system) and made speaking in Qazaq a sign of low status. Moreover, the Qazaq accent when speaking Russian was a reason for ridicule, discrimination and even denial of employment.²⁵ Apart from members of small circles of the Soviet Qazaq intelligentsia and ethnic Qazaq “nomenklatura”, who lived in their enclaves in Alma-Ata, the Soviet institute of “propiska” was widely used to keep ethnic Qazaqs out of the major cities and Qazaq language was denied its place in the public sphere in cities (for example, there was only one Qazaq secondary school in Soviet Alma-Ata before the 1980s).

Overall, in the post-2022 period, a new stage of reconsidering and reappraising the Soviet period, especially the Stalinist period, started in Qazaqstan (importantly, in September 2023, Qazaqstan’s archives, specifically KGB documents, were opened to public,²⁶ and a Qazaq expert in the field of the Stalinist purges was appointed as the head of the archive). Also, past discriminatory practices were openly discussed for the first time, especially in the Russian-language media, though in Qazaq-medium circles they have been discussed for years. For example, the recent publication of *Vlast* quotes a Qazaq activist, a participant in the December 1986 Almaty uprising, “In Soviet times, ethnic Qazaqs felt like a “third-class people”. It was impossible to get a job without knowing

Russian. For a Qazaq, getting an apartment in the city was like flying to the moon”.²⁷

Was the Catastrophic Famine of the Soviet Period (“Asharshylyq”) a Physical and Cultural Genocide of Qazaqs?

The manmade famine in Qazaqstan (called “Asharshylyq” in Qazaq) perpetrated by the Soviet regime is relatively well-researched in Qazaqstan and in Western academia (the first publications appeared during the perestroika period, such as the edited volume *Naubet* (in Qazaq, “Catastrophe”), of which only the first edition of thirty thousand copies was printed in 1990, and Smagul Yelubai’s novel *Aqboz Uy* (in Qazaq, “Whitish house” or Qazaq yurt covered by white felt, used by the author as a symbol of the tragic fate of ordinary Qazaq family) about the famine and the Stalinist purges, which was also published in 1990. Since then, much more research has been published, including the research of foreign authors such as “The Hungry Steppe: Famine, Violence, and the Making of Soviet Kazakhstan” by US scholar Sarah Cameron).

The research, based on archival documents from the funds of the Soviet state agency in charge of requisitioning and distributing meat and livestock, demonstrates the Soviet regime’s intention to target Qazaqs deliberately (intention to harm and eventually to eradicate an entire group of people is a crucial component of the crime of genocide).²⁸ The famine began in Qazaqstan due to grain and livestock requisitions carried out in 1928–1930, which in 1931 (Qazaq experts accept that the famine lasted from 1928 to the end of 1933, not only in the 1931–1933 period²⁹) turned into the largest mass death event in the history of Central Asia, and a great famine comparable in the USSR only to the Ukrainian Holodomor.³⁰ Overall, the Qazaq population in the 1930s was consciously sacrificed to the *raison d’état* of a Soviet imperial hierarchy, where Qazaqs were placed at the bottom of the Soviet consumption hierarchy pyramid.³¹ As Madi Kapparov observes, “Let me be clear: it was a genocide”.³²

An estimated 32 to 42% of all Qazaq people

PHOTO: NAZARBAYEV UNIVERSITY

On December 19, 2023, a ceremonial presentation of the first Oxford Qazaq Dictionary, developed by the International Society “Kazak tili” on behalf of the President of Kazakhstan Kasym-Jomart Tokayev, took place at Nazarbayev University.

died, the highest percentage of any ethnic group killed by the Soviet famine. Some regions became depopulated, especially in Northern and Central Qazaqstan, where later the GULAG camps were established. Many Qazaq sources claim that half of the population perished because, besides famine, many died subsequently as a result of disease and hard work in the Ural and Siberian regions of Russia, especially in mines and new constructions sites, where hundreds of thousands of Qazaqs fled. Also, many Qazaqs were killed by the Red Army when they tried to out-migrate to China, Iran, and Afghanistan — famine led to the exodus of more than one million Qazaqs.³³

In the period before 2022, there was a severe lack of research that applied the decolonial perspective to the Qazaq famine. Moreover, the term genocide was used hesitantly because the Qazaq political elites took the position of “not politicizing the famine” due to “friendly” relations with Russia, which tended towards rehabilitation of Soviet crimes and Stalinism.³⁴ However, independent Qazaq media, social activists and historians did not shy away from using the term genocide even before 2022.³⁵

After February 2022, the discussion about Asharshylyq evolved from a specific topic researched by historians, of interest to social activists and discussed in family circles (almost all ethnic Qazaq families living in present-day Qazaqstan were affected by the famine and subsequent exodus) to a topic of societal interest. The application of the concept of genocide and

ethnocide to “Asharshylyq” became more and more routine.³⁶

Thus the solidarity of Qazaq people with Ukrainians is rooted in this dark side of Soviet history. The efforts and eventual success of Ukrainians in getting Holodomor accepted as a genocide have been observed by Qazaq society with deep understanding and empathy.³⁷

Besides physical genocide, Soviet policy in Qazaqstan also implemented cultural genocide because Soviet collectivization deliberately targeted the Qazaq nomadic culture; hence its habitat was violently destroyed in many parts of Qazaqstan. In other words, the Soviet regime deliberately destroyed the structures and environment that allowed Qazaqs to live as a distinct group; these are the constituent components of cultural genocide.

The need for new reassessments of “Asharshylyq” and destruction of Qazaq-Eurasian nomadism is a humanistic task of restoring historical justice and healing generational traumas, but it is not about solidifying a sense of victimhood. Notably, the enmity towards Qazaq nomadic culture was inherent to the colonial policies of the Tsarist rule and the Soviet system (nomadic culture is inherently antagonistic to subjugation. Even the word “Qazaq” has a meaning: “free riding”) and it was manifested, inter alia, in constraining and attempting to eradicate the Qazaq tradition of breeding horses. An example of the decolonial turn in Qazaqstan is the revival of the Qazaq tradition

“The Qazaq accent when speaking Russian was a reason for ridicule, discrimination and even denial of employment.”

Tazys are used in Kazakhstan primarily for hunting and are considered one of the oldest dog breeds in the world. It is one of the national dog breeds that the Qazaq government now wants to preserve. Photo from 1930. PHOTO: WIKIMEDIA COMMONS

of breeding horses and greyhounds, and of Qazaq handicrafts and folklore, which “all were attempted to be destroyed by Soviet policy”. In the post-winter 2022 period, Qazaqstan adopted official measures to revive Qazaq dog breeds; e.g., in December 2022 the parliament approved the law on the preservation of Tazy and Tobet dog breeds,³⁸ and to protect Qazaq horse breeds such as the Aday horse.³⁹

“Decolonization” of the Qazaq Language in the Post-February 2022 Period

Considering the Qazaq language as “lesser” or “underdeveloped” and letting it become marginalized (as a manifestation of Soviet colonization) was ended mainly in the post-winter 2022 period. For many Russian-speaking Qazaqs, the start of the war in Ukraine became a turning point. Thus, the mental barriers to learning and speaking in Qazaq have disappeared, which means that paradoxically, the problem of the Qazaq language was solved smoothly and naturally in parallel to the ongoing process of the decolonization of the mind.⁴⁰

Like nothing else, solving the Qazaq language problem naturally bridges the gaps between Russian-speaking and Qazaq-speaking Qazaqs. Importantly, since February 2022, the use of pejorative words like “mambet” (used to mock

rural Qazaq-speaking persons), and “shala qazaq” (literally meaning, “not real Qazaq”, a derogatory word used to downgrade Russian-speaking Qazaqs) has almost disappeared, according to the observations of some Qazaq journalists and youth activists voiced during the meetings organized by the Erkin Adamdar [in Qazaq, “free people”] Foundation, which is composed of independent scholars, journalists, poets and artisans, in Almaty in 2022 and 2023, as well as my personal communication with 1st and 4th year students in Almaty.

It can be argued that Russian-speaking Qazaqs, having been exposed more intensively to Russification, felt the sense of coloniality more intimately. It is logical and understandable that in the “decolonial Qazaq wave” Russian-speaking and bilingual Qazaq journalists, businesspersons, academics, and activists are playing a leading role. For example, Qazaq media outlets that initially published only in Russian (like Exclusive.kz, Vlast.kz, the-village.kz, Steppe and many others) switched to using Qazaq as well and enthusiastically promote the decolonial agenda.

With the start of mobilization in Russia in late September 2022, many Russian citizens of Asian origin such as Saha, Buryats, and Kalmyks fled to Qazaqstan (e.g., in only one day one thousand young Kalmyk men crossed the Russian-Qazaq border in Atyrau oblast⁴¹). Many of them and those who moved before mobilization note the systemic discrimination in Russia and express the desire to try to stay in Qazaqstan even if the war ends.⁴² The influx of these people, who are Russian-speaking but fleeing from chauvinism, also pushed many Russian-speaking Qazaqs to reassess their positionality.

It can be argued that the war in Ukraine encouraged different groups in Qazaqstan to move towards more consolidation and building a strong political nation. The sense of preserving the common homeland and identity in the face of threat, the sense of being united by language, shared history, and ancestry, turned out to be crucial to uniting linguistically and culturally distant groups in Qazaqstan. The unified and harsh responses of Qazaq nation-

alistic, liberal, feminist and queer groups (of both Qazaq-speaking and Russian-speaking spectrums) to public provocations by Russian propagandists⁴³ or the unified responses to abusive comments about speaking in Qazaq made by the Russian citizen and CEO of Chocholife operating in Qazaqstan, and his public “canceling” by diverse Qazaq groups,⁴⁴ forged more intra-Qazaq consolidation.

Overall, after the start of the full-scale Russian aggression against Ukraine in February 2022, previously observed cleavages between Russian-speaking and Qazaq-speaking ethnic Qazaqs began disappearing to a marked extent. The divisions between the two groups are becoming blurred because of the disappearance of the mental barriers to learn and speak Qazaq, the development of bilingualism, the emergence of new generations who are fluent in Qazaq, and the gradual strengthening of the Qazaq language’s position in the public space, academia, and education (these are my observations based on interaction with students and grassroots NGOs). Furthermore, the phenomenon of the “Russian-speaking Qazaq, who does not know Qazaq at all” is becoming history. However, the large ethnic Qazaq community in the Russian Federation (who live in their ancestral lands adjacent to Qazaqstan territories) is still under the threat of Russification.

A similar consolidation can be observed, to a degree, between ethnic Qazaqs and other ethnic groups. The most serious challenge to the decolonial turn in Qazaqstan may come from the senior generation of ethnic Russians, who consume information produced by Russian propagandists. However, the attitude of the younger generation of Qazaqstani Russians, though it is impossible to present them as a uniform group, is more favorable toward being a part of the Qazaqstani state and nation because of their exposure to different information and their socialization in a more pluralistic environment shaped by Qazaqs. In the spring and summer of 2022, many young Qazaqstani Russians produced flash-mobs declaring, “We are local, Qazaqstani Russians!” and “We don’t need to be saved!”⁴⁵ Some Russian activists, like Alexey Skalozubov⁴⁶, have established centers through-

out Qazaqstan to learn the Qazaq language. The threat from expansionist and revisionist powers serves to build bridges and to unite on the grounds of common citizenship, history, and experiences, regardless of origin and way of life.

An “a-cultural” Russian Language in Qazaqstan

The Russian language in Qazaqstan is increasingly becoming an “a-cultural” language (used irrespective of a particular culture), which is detached from the Russian state and Russian politics and represents a separate cultural and social phenomenon peculiar to Qazaqstan (further research is required here). One manifestation of this is the existence of large groups of bilingual and Russian-speaking Qazaqs and non-Qazaqs who associate their life with Qazaqstan and Qazaq culture and oppose Russia’s colonial policies and aggression against Ukraine. The gradual strengthening of the Qazaq language in the public sphere and the emergence of the “a-cultural” Russian language are not oxymoronic but in opposite the two sides of one whole produced by the Qazaq decolonial turn.

To summarize, the divisions between Qazaq-speaking and Russian-speaking Qazaqs are closing, which will lead to the gradual disappearance of major cleavages between these groups because of combined phenomena that emerged in the post-winter 2022 period, such as the “decolonization” of the Qazaq language, a “Qazaq decolonial turn” leading to building an inclusive Qazaq identity (among other things, critical of archaic traditions and social norms; see below), the sense of unity in the face of the threat from a big neighboring country waging war against another country with which Qazaq society feels deep empathy and strong solidarity.

Decoloniality and Inclusive Qazaq Identity

The decolonial turn in the questions and discussions about culture and identity in Qazaqstan lead to some bigger issues: “What kind of nation/country (inclusive or exclusive, democratic or non-democratic) do we want to be and what kind of citizens do we want to

“It can be argued that the war in Ukraine encouraged different groups in Qazaqstan to move towards more consolidation and building a strong political nation.”

become?” This paper argues that decoloniality also means the creation of an inclusive, human rights-friendly culture, religion and identity.⁴⁷ These ideas have been articulated during public discussions organized by various Qazaq NGOs such as the Erkin Adamdar Foundation,⁴⁸ as well as during public discussions with such NGOs as Civil Kezdesu⁴⁹ (in Qazaq “meeting”). Hence, the decolonial turn will help develop an inclusive Qazaq identity, which is open to accepting different perceptions of cultural, social, religious and gender identities and by extension inclusive models of nation-building. In other words, it is about constructing a human rights-friendly individual and group identity.

Nationalistic and conservative Qazaq groups (an integral part of what is called “deep Qazaq society”) are naturally distant, even antagonistic, to Russian colonialism and the idea of the “Russian world” (“Russkiy mir”), but they are also exclusivist in cultural, religious, ethnic, and language terms. However, the war in Ukraine shows that there is no alternative to dialogue and eventual acceptance of each other for either Qazaq nationalistic, conservative groups or the “cosmopolitan”, Qazaq-feminist, Qazaq-queer groups. Qazaq feminist and queer groups, who are among the most anti-war and decolonial-inclined, may find common ground with Qazaq conservative groups in their anti-war position and anti-colonial aspirations. On the other hand, conservative Qazaq groups are gradually realizing that the anti-human rights discourses and geo-politicization of human rights and democratic values are the results of the propaganda spread around the world by the authoritarian revisionist regimes.⁵⁰

Embracing the Legacy of Alash Intellectuals

In the post-winter 2022 period in Qazaqstan, the acceptance of the legacy of Alash intellectuals and Jadids, exterminated by the Stalinist system, is being more robustly articulated.⁵¹

Jadidism broadly can be conceptualized as a pro-human rights (in today’s conceptualization), educational, social, and political movement of the Eurasian Muslims. The anti-colonial Alash movement was predominantly Qazaq,

but it had almost the same progressive-reformist Muslim, pro-human rights agenda of Jadidism and adopted social-democratic ideas.⁵² Alash intellectuals created an intellectual, religious, and literary tradition with a distinctive language to defend and protect universal human dignity.⁵³ These intellectuals can be seen as the first generation of “democratic-liberal Qazaqs”.⁵⁴ During the Perestroika period and in the early period of post-Soviet independence, the legacy of these intellectuals was mainly explored and promoted by the Qazaq-speaking community; however, in post-winter 2022, Russian-speaking Qazaq intellectuals and activists also turned to these intellectuals. This embracement by most of Qazaq society can be seen as another dimension of Qazaq decolonial turn.

Sobering Up to the International Political and Economic System

In Qazaqstan, the reevaluations of “Bloody January” 2022 and the war in Ukraine led to what this article calls “sobering” up to, even disillusionment with, the international political and economic system. There was a synergy between the creation of a consolidated authoritarian regime and neoliberal reforms in Qazaqstan in the 1990s.⁵⁵ Neoliberal rentier capitalism facilitated the emergence and provided the grounds for developing the plutocratic authoritarian regimes since the marketization reforms, foremost privatization, led to the emergence of the immense political capital of the rich and helped create plutocracy in place of democracy.⁵⁶ “Peripheral” countries rich in natural resources and agricultural production, such as Ukraine and Qazaqstan, are faced with a structural injustice (resulting from the international division of labor, capital, income and knowledge production of today’s capitalist system) that pushes them into a disadvantaged position, which can be called economic, financial, technological and academic colonization.

Nazarbayev’s regime used close engagement with the international neoliberal economic system to consolidate its power and increase its wealth, which by default led to the impoverishment of ordinary citizens; all these issues are widely discussed in Qazaqstan.

Since February 2022, the world has been experiencing an accelerated arms race (including nuclear armament) and expansion of the security alliances, foremost NATO. However, a single factor — Ukraine with a nuclear arsenal, or, as a very optimistic scenario, the real guarantees given by the Western nuclear powers, the USA, the UK, and France to Ukraine (and by extension to Qazaqstan) could have prevented all these negative phenomena: first and foremost, full-scale war in Ukraine. Therefore, the unfairness, even coloniality, of the international political system became more pronounced in Qazaqstan in parallel to the outbreak of war in Ukraine.

As mentioned above, the Budapest Memorandum on security assurances to respect independence and territorial integrity of the denuclearized post-Soviet states — Ukraine and Qazaqstan turned out to be a toothless declaration (though it was described as a set of high-level political commitments) to pacify the security concerns of Ukraine and Qazaqstan. Since the annexation of Crimea in 2014 and especially since the full-scale aggression against Ukraine, this document has been under scrutiny in Qazaqstan. Qazaq experts have noted its “vague diplomatic” and “hypocritical” wording. What baffles many in Qazaqstan is that Western policymakers hastened to explain that “assurances” are NOT “guarantees” of Ukraine’s (and logically of Qazaqstan’s) sovereignty and territorial inviolability.⁵⁷ This situation begs the question, “Was not the de-nuclearization of Ukraine and Qazaqstan in 1994 in exchange for “non-existent” guarantees of the nuclear club members proof of a colonial international political system?”

On the other hand, according to Qazaqs, the international political system’s colonial hierarchical nature can also be seen in the insufficient and ineffective military assistance given to Ukraine, which prolongs the war and leads to unjustifiable civilian and military casualties. Independent Qazaq media wrote that Western countries’ aid to Ukraine is just at the level not to lose the war but not to win it either.⁵⁸ Ukrainian observers emphasize

that Ukraine is actively prevented from being too successful in its war with Russia. All these indicate the scale of geopolitical change needed to restore peace and security and help Ukraine in fighting the aggressor.⁵⁹

Last but not least, the situation in the Palestinian territories, the excessive, disproportionate use of force against the population in Gaza by Israel and its support by major Western powers, led many in Qazaqstan to question the double standards of the major powers of the international political system. While Qazaq society supports Ukraine and condemns the war crimes committed by Hamas, it also feels deep sympathy and supports the Palestinian people in their struggle for self-determination (Qazaqstan provided humanitarian aid to the population of Gaza in November and December 2023) and condemns the war crimes committed by Israel.

Conclusion

In the Central Asian region, specifically in Qazaqstan, not only is the condemnation of aggression and general solidarity with and empathy for Ukrainian people more evident, but also the demands for decolonization and decoloniality are louder and more assertive. Therefore, as the main idea of this paper claims, due to the growing awareness of colonialism and coloniality, we can talk about a mental separation from revisionist Russia and the colonial Soviet past taking place in Qazaqstan. Moreover, we can talk about the emerging Qazaq voice or the Qazaq wave of decoloniality. However, all these should not be seen as leading to claiming vengeance and internalizing the sense of victimhood; on the contrary, as this article tries to convey, this awakening is about lightening up the spirit of creating new, more inclusive perceptions and models of Qazaq identity, culture and nation.

It can be claimed that the decolonial turn in Qazaqstan, which tries to revive the legacy of Alash and Jadid intellectuals, can provide good support for the universality of human rights and the universality of human dignity in today’s critical juncture when respect for human rights, peaceful cooperation, and democratic values are under significant threat. In today’s world,

” This embracement by most of Qazaq society can be seen as another dimension of Qazaq decolonial turn.

human rights and democratic values should not be monopolized by any culture or civilization; in the end, it is dangerous and harmful to this culture and civilization itself. The decolonial voice of countries like Qazaqstan, which is Asian, Eurasian, and Muslim-majority, is important to support the struggle for universal human dignity and to uphold human rights and democratic values today, where the autocratic and militaristic powers are trying to subvert and appropriate the decolonial agenda and human rights. For all this, the support and solidarity of Qazaqstan with Ukraine is very important.

Overall, Ukrainians and Qazaqs are united by their strong will to survive all hardships, remain a distinct community and develop a democratic nation despite their difficult geo-strategic location, dramatic history, and external and internal challenges. ●

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